

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN DEVELOPING TOURISM STUDENTS' CRITICAL LISTENING SKILLS

Khodjakulova Nargiza Khosiyatkulovna

First year PhD student, "TIAME"NRU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085184>

Abstract. *Listening skill is the process to accurately receive and interpret spoken or non-verbal messages during communication. It involves not just hearing what someone is saying, but also understanding the meaning behind their words, empathizing with their perspective, and providing appropriate feedback. Effective listening is essential in various contexts, including personal relationships, professional settings, and academic environments. This article is about the role of teachers in developing tourism students' critical listening skills. As we know nowadays tourism is one of the developing sphere in Uzbekistan. The students who study in this field should improve listening skills more than other skills. Last statistics show that people spend their 45% of time on listening than speaking. People who work in this sphere should acquire their listening skills more as well.*

Keywords: *listening, critical listening, tourism, teacher creativity*

Introduction

There are a lot of meanings of the term "listening". Chastain (1971) said that the aim of listening comprehension is to comprehend the language at normal speed in an automatic condition. Hamouda (2013) said that listening skill is very important in acquiring understandable input. Learning does not occur if there is not any input. Pourhosein Gilakjani and Mohammadreza Ahmadi (2011) claimed that listening has an crucial role in the communication process. According to Pourhosein Gilakjani and Seyedeh Masoumeh Ahmadi (2011), out the four main areas of communication skills called listening, speaking, reading, and writing, listening is the most significant of all. Goss (1982) said that in listening comprehension listeners try to build a meaning when they get the information from the listening source.

There are several components to good listening skills, including paying attention, interpreting messages, remembering information, and responding empathetically. Effective listening involves more than just hearing words – it requires focus, concentration, and the ability to pick up on subtle cues such as tone of voice, body language, and facial expressions.

Developing strong listening skills can improve relationships, enhance problem-solving abilities, and boost overall communication effectiveness. It is important to practice active listening by demonstrating interest, asking clarifying questions, and providing feedback to ensure mutual understanding. Overall, listening skill is a crucial aspect of effective communication that can greatly benefit both personal and professional relationships.

Literature review

Wilson says (2010) listening is the process of actively receiving, interpreting, and understanding spoken or non-verbal messages. It involves not only hearing the words that are spoken, but also paying attention to the speaker's tone of voice, body language, and context to fully comprehend their message.

This chart above stresses that the importance of listening as a communication skill. A typical study points out that many of us spend 70 to 80 percent of our time in some form of communication. Of that time, we spend about **20** percent writing, **15** percent reading, **25** percent speaking, and **40** percent listening. (<https://communispond.com/listening-improving-the-most-used-communication-skill/>)

Listening is an essential receptive skill used to communicate which enables us to completely understand matters we hear and come up with appropriate feedback, the ability to accurately receive and interpret messages in the communication process.

The chart below shows Listening is a process. This process is divided into several stages: (Anderson (1972))

There are differences between hearing and listening worth touching on: one “**hears**” with one’s **brains**, not only with one’s **ears**. Hearing is the act of perceiving sound by the ear. Listening is a conscious mental process, as much about the brain as the ear, and it starts with establishing attention to a sound

As we face the variety of global problems such as climate changes, economic disparities, and social injustice, the world needs listening skills more than ever. Listening skills are one of the

core life skills that are critical in life, work, and school. Listening skills enable children to access information, develop other skills, such as empathy, and critical thinking, and have better academic performances and lives. Listening skills are one of the most desired and needed in workplaces. (Andrew D.,)

Figure 1. Effective listening requires

Steinberg (2007) and Azmi Bingol, Celik, Yidliz, and Tugrul Mart (2014) defined listening is a crucial communication skill that allows individuals to build relationships and connect with others. Gain information and knowledge. Resolve conflicts and misunderstandings. Provide support and empathy. Learn and grow both personally and professionally

Figure 2. According to Morley (2001) and Rost (2001) There are different types of listening, depending on the situation and purpose.

By developing strong listening skills, individuals can enhance their communication abilities, build stronger relationships, and achieve greater success in both personal and professional settings.

So far in EFL classes there have been focuses on comprehensive listening and tasks have been developed to check students' understanding the facts or details in audio and audio-visual materials. Unfortunately, there is a lack of attention to critical listening skills.

What is critical listening?

According to Moore and Parker (2012), "critical listening is an advanced form of listening that involves analyzing, evaluating, and interpreting the content of a message, as well as assessing the credibility and intentions of the speaker". Unlike passive listening, which involves simply receiving information, critical listening requires active engagement and cognitive processing to discern the validity, logic, and evidence presented by the speaker. Critical listeners employ skills such as questioning, skepticism, and logical reasoning to evaluate the accuracy, coherence, and persuasiveness of the message. This form of listening is essential in contexts such as academic discourse, political debates, media consumption, and decision-making, as it enables individuals to discern truth from misinformation, identify persuasive techniques, and make informed judgments.

Who developed critical listening

The concept of critical listening has evolved over time through the contributions of various scholars and researchers in fields such as communication, psychology, education, and philosophy. While there isn't a single individual attributed to its development, several influential figures have contributed to the understanding and practice of critical listening.

Some early influences on critical listening can be traced back to ancient Greek philosophers such as Socrates, who emphasized the importance of questioning and critical inquiry in the pursuit of knowledge. In more recent times, scholars like John Dewey, known for his work on reflective thinking and inquiry-based learning, laid the groundwork for critical thinking skills, which are closely related to critical listening.

Additionally, researchers in the field of communication studies, such as Ralph G. Nichols and Irving B. Weiner, have contributed to the understanding of listening processes and the development of listening skills. Their work has helped shape the concept of critical listening by highlighting the importance of analyzing and evaluating the information received during the listening process.

Methodology

The research design for this work is to find out;

- the role of communicative language teaching approach in developing critical listening skills;

-the role of teacher creativity in developing students' critical listening skills;

-the effects of improving tourism students' critical listening skills

In communicative language teaching (CLT), critical listening plays a crucial role in developing learners' ability to comprehend and engage with spoken language in authentic communication contexts. The concept of critical listening within the framework of CLT, examining its definition, characteristics, pedagogical approaches, and implications for language learning and teaching.

Definition and Characteristics of Critical Listening in CLT

Critical listening in CLT involves actively analyzing, evaluating, and interpreting spoken language to comprehend meaning and engage in meaningful communication. Learners are encouraged to go beyond surface-level comprehension and consider factors such as tone, intonation, implied meaning, and cultural context. Critical listeners in CLT engage in activities that require them to discern main ideas, infer meaning from context, evaluate speaker intentions, and respond thoughtfully to spoken discourse.

Pedagogical Approaches to Developing Critical Listening Skills in CLT

In CLT, educators employ a variety of pedagogical approaches to foster critical listening skills among learners. These approaches may include:

Authentic Materials: Using authentic audio materials, such as podcasts, interviews, and speeches, allows learners to engage with real-life language use and develop their ability to comprehend and analyze spoken discourse.

Task-based Learning: Task-based learning activities, such as listening for specific information, summarizing main points, and discussing opinions, provide opportunities for learners to practice critical listening in meaningful contexts.

Interactive Listening Tasks: Interactive listening tasks, such as role-plays, debates, and simulations, encourage learners to actively engage with spoken language, respond critically, and negotiate meaning with others.

Reflective Practice: Reflective activities, such as journaling and group discussions, help learners reflect on their listening experiences, identify areas for improvement, and develop metacognitive strategies for effective listening.

Implications for Language Learning and Teaching

Developing critical listening skills in CLT has several implications for language learning and teaching. By equipping learners with the ability to critically analyze and evaluate spoken language, CLT promotes not only linguistic competence but also critical thinking skills, cultural awareness, and effective communication strategies. Learners who develop strong critical listening skills are better prepared to engage in authentic communication in diverse linguistic and cultural contexts.

Teacher creativity plays a crucial role in facilitating effective learning experiences, especially in developing critical listening skills among students. This literature review explores the concept of teacher creativity in teaching critical listening, examining its definition, characteristics, strategies, and implications for pedagogy.

Definition and Characteristics of Teacher Creativity in Teaching Critical Listening

Teacher creativity in teaching critical listening involves the innovative and resourceful use of instructional methods, materials, and approaches to engage students in meaningful listening experiences. Creative teachers design activities that stimulate students' curiosity, critical thinking, and active participation in the listening process. Characteristics of teacher creativity in this context include adaptability, originality, and responsiveness to students' diverse learning needs and interests.

Strategies for Fostering Teacher Creativity in Teaching Critical Listening

Several strategies can enhance teacher creativity in teaching critical listening:

Integration of Multimedia: Creative teachers incorporate multimedia resources such as audio clips, videos, and interactive simulations to create dynamic and immersive listening activities that capture students' attention and interest.

Interactive and Collaborative Activities: Creative teachers design interactive and collaborative listening tasks, such as group discussions, role-plays, and problem-solving activities, that encourage students to actively engage with the material and construct meaning collaboratively.

“Incorporation of Real-life Contexts”: Creative teachers contextualize listening activities within real-life situations, such as authentic conversations, news broadcasts, and podcasts, to make the listening experience relevant and meaningful for students.

“Use of Creative Prompts and Questions”: Creative teachers employ open-ended prompts and thought-provoking questions to stimulate students' critical thinking and encourage them to reflect on the content, context, and implications of the listening material.

Implications for Pedagogy

Teacher creativity in teaching critical listening has several implications for pedagogy:

“Enhanced Student Engagement: Creative teaching methods captivate students' interest and motivation, fostering active participation and deeper engagement with the listening material.

“Development of Critical Thinking Skills”: Creative listening activities promote critical thinking skills such as analysis, evaluation, and synthesis, empowering students to become discerning listeners who can critically assess and interpret spoken discourse.

“Fostering of Creativity in Students”: Creative teaching practices inspire students to think creatively and explore alternative perspectives, cultivating their own creativity in listening and communication.

What is the role of critical listening for tourism students?

In the context of tourism, critical listening can play a significant role in enhancing the overall visitor experience and satisfaction. By actively listening to the needs, preferences, and feedback of tourists, hospitality professionals can tailor their services to meet customer expectations effectively. Critical listening skills enable tourism professionals to understand the diverse perspectives and cultural backgrounds of visitors, leading to improved communication and rapport with guests.

Moreover, in the tourism industry, critical listening can aid in resolving conflicts, addressing complaints, and managing customer expectations. By attentively listening to tourists' concerns and feedback, businesses can identify areas for improvement and implement strategies to enhance the quality of their services. This proactive approach can help tourism organizations build long-lasting relationships with customers and foster loyalty within the industry.

In summary, critical listening in tourism is essential for providing personalized and high-quality experiences to visitors, fostering positive relationships with customers, and continuously improving service standards within the tourism sector.

Critical listening plays a crucial role in the field of law as it involves carefully analyzing and evaluating information presented during legal proceedings, such as court hearings, depositions, and client consultations. By actively listening to verbal and non-verbal cues, legal professionals can accurately understand the nuances of a case, identify key points, and make informed decisions. Critical listening helps lawyers to effectively communicate with clients, witnesses, and other parties involved in a legal matter, ensuring that all relevant information is considered and addressed appropriately. Additionally, it enables legal professionals to assess the credibility of testimonies, detect inconsistencies, and formulate persuasive arguments based on the

information gathered. In summary, critical listening is essential for legal practitioners to navigate complex legal issues, advocate for their clients, and uphold the principles of justice.

There are several components to good listening skills, including paying attention, interpreting messages, remembering information, and responding empathetically. Effective listening involves more than just hearing words – it requires focus, concentration, and the ability to pick up on subtle cues such as tone of voice, body language, and facial expressions.

Developing strong listening skills can improve relationships, enhance problem-solving abilities, and boost overall communication effectiveness. It is important to practice active listening by demonstrating interest, asking clarifying questions, and providing feedback to ensure mutual understanding. Overall, listening skill is a crucial aspect of effective communication that can greatly benefit both personal and professional relationships.

Teachers play a crucial role in developing tourism students' critical listening skills. Critical listening is essential in the tourism industry as it involves actively analyzing and evaluating information to make informed decisions and provide excellent customer service. Here are some ways teachers can help develop these skills:

Creating Engaging Learning Activities: Teachers can design activities that require students to listen critically to tourism-related content such as customer inquiries, cultural presentations, or industry experts. These activities can include listening exercises, role-plays, and simulations to help students practice active listening and analytical skills.

Providing Feedback: Teachers can offer constructive feedback on students' listening skills, highlighting areas for improvement and encouraging reflective practice. Feedback can help students understand their strengths and weaknesses in listening and guide them towards enhancing their critical listening abilities.

Incorporating Real-world Scenarios: Teachers can integrate real-world scenarios into their teaching, such as case studies, industry guest speakers, or field trips. By exposing students to authentic listening situations, teachers can help them develop the ability to discern important information, identify key points, and make sound judgments based on what they hear.

Promoting Discussion and Debate: Encouraging class discussions and debates on tourism-related topics can help students practice active listening, critical thinking, and articulating their viewpoints based on what they have heard. This fosters a deeper understanding of diverse perspectives within the tourism industry and enhances students' ability to engage critically with different viewpoints.

Utilizing Technology: Teachers can leverage technology such as audiovisual materials, podcasts, online resources, and interactive platforms to engage students in listening exercises. Technology can provide a dynamic and immersive learning experience, allowing students to practice critical listening skills in various formats and contexts.

By incorporating these strategies and emphasizing the importance of critical listening in the tourism industry, teachers can empower students to become adept listeners who can effectively navigate complex information, communicate with stakeholders, and excel in their careers in the tourism sector."

Conclusion

Critical listening is an essential component of communicative language teaching, enabling learners to comprehend and engage with spoken language in authentic communication contexts. By incorporating pedagogical approaches that foster critical listening skills, educators can

empower learners to become proficient and reflective listeners who are capable of navigating the complexities of real-life communication.

Teacher creativity plays a vital role in cultivating critical listening skills among students. By adopting innovative instructional strategies and approaches, teachers can create dynamic and engaging listening experiences that stimulate students' curiosity, critical thinking, and active participation. Fostering teacher creativity in teaching critical listening has the potential to enhance student engagement, develop critical thinking skills, and foster creativity in communication.

Further research could explore the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches to developing critical listening skills in CLT and investigate the relationship between critical listening proficiency and overall language proficiency among learners and the impact of specific creative teaching approaches on students' critical listening proficiency and investigate effective strategies for fostering teacher creativity in diverse educational contexts.

REFERENCES

1. Skills for Life: Listening, Andrew D. Wolvin, JungKyu Rhys Lim, 11 Jul 2022
2. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy*. Pearson Education.
3. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Vandergrift, L. (2007). Recent developments in second and foreign language listening comprehension research. *Language Teaching*, 40(3), 191-210.
5. Craft, A. (2005). *Creativity in schools: Tensions and dilemmas*. Routledge.
6. Sawyer, R. K. (2012). *Explaining creativity: The science of human innovation*. Oxford University Press
7. Sternberg, R. J. (2003). *Wisdom, intelligence, and creativity synthesized*. Cambridge University Press.